

A LITERATURE REVIEW OF PRAJASTHAPANA MAHAKASHAYA

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ABSTRACT

Reproduction is the biological process by which new individual organism's "offspring" are produced from their parent. It is the dream of every individual to get healthy and intellectual Baby. Ayurveda has very strong beliefs it is possible to get the Desired offspring by the rituals as well as few medicinal practices. In this review the drugs referred under the heading of prajasthapana mahakashaya which have been mentioned in charak Samhita and these drugs have the significance to contribute desired nature of child if the parent adopt the practice once after the purification of body as well as taking rejuvinyatory (i.e Rasayana Aushadhi). Here is an attempt to made to explain the therapeutic use of Prajasthapana mahakashaya.

KEYWORDS: Charakokta mahakashaya, prajasthapana, Ayurveda.

INTRODUCTION

Selection of proper drug in the management of disease or appropriate condition is very important. Drug is an important part of *chikista chatushpada* which has been placed at 2nd place just after the physician (*Vaidya*) in *charak Samhita*. The comprehensive knowledge of medicine (*drug*) is very important to physician because without knowledge of the drug the patient can't be treated properly.

The ayurvedic classical text have described the pharmacological classification of drugs. the karmanusar classification of charak has been done in 50 *mahakashaya* which have been mentioned in *charak Samhita sutra 4. Prajasthapana mahakashaya* contain 10 drugs which are- *Aindri, Brahmi, Shataveerya, Sahastraveerya, Amogha, Avyatha, Shiva, Arishta, Vatyapushpi, Wishwasenkanta*. Those drugs which increase the fertility of female is known as

prajasthapak. The Active principles present in this drugs act as a fertility modulator. Detail study of these drugs i.e *Rasa, Guna, Veerya, Vipak, Doshagnata*, Action on *dhatu*s and *Roghnata* is done. These drugs having some specific action known as "*Prabhav*". It also has *rasayana* properties which it improves the qualities of *dhatu*s and improves rejuvenation. *Charak* and *Kashyap* have prescribed certain drugs during pregnancy without specifying their indications, period or method of use. *chakrapani* has clarified that *garbhashtapana* drugs are those which after counteracting the effect of harmful factors (*garbhopaghatakar* for fetus help in its proper maintenance *bhavas*) thus these can be considered even as treatment for abortion.^[3]

PRAJASTHAPNA DRUGS

1. *Aindri* (*Centella Asiatica*)^[4]

-It helps in *Artavajanan*. It works on menstrual diseases thus helps in conception.

- Acharya *Charak* included the *Aindri* in *Balya, Prajasthapana, Vayasthapana*, and *Shonitasthapana mahakashaya*.

-Antidepressant, neuroprotective and antioxidant activity.

2. *Brahmi* (*Bacopa monnieri*)

-It works as *Stanyajanan* and *Stanyashodhana*.

-Acharya *Charaka* has described it as nerve tonic, improves the brain cell Functions. And hence used in various mental conditions leading to psychosis.

-This drug is also used as tonic and foetus growth promoting drug.

-Antistress, Antioxidants effects of *Bacosides* of *B. monnieri*.^[5]

3. *Shatavari* (*Asparagus racemosus*)

-Acharya *Charaka* included this drug in *Balya, Shukrajanan, Prajasthapana* and *Vayasthapana Mahakashayas*.

-An oestrogenic effect of *Shatavari* on the female mammary gland and Genital organs.^[6]

-A glycoside, *Shatavarin I*, isolated from the root of *A. racemosus* has been found to be responsible for the competitive block of oxytocin-induced contraction.

-It is galactagogue, antioxidant, immune stimulant, aphrodisiac, diuretic, helps in anorexia, insomnia, antifungal, anti tussive, hypotensive. The active compounds are *satavarin*, *asparagamine*. And in roots and *sarsapogenin*, *sitosterol*, *stema sterol* in aerial parts.

4. *Doorva* (*Cynodon dactylon*)

- It acts as Raktastambhaka.
- Acharya Charaka has mentioned this in *Varnya Mahakashay*.
- Acharya Sushruta described *Doorva* in *Pitta shaman*.
- Acharya Vagbhat included as *Pitta shaman*.
- The plant extract checks uterine bleeding, strengthens the uterus, averts abortion and augments of foetal growth.
- Ethanol extract of *C. dactylon* has also marked CNS depressant and antioxidant activities.^[7]
- The active constituents are triticin oil, agropyrene, furfural, arunodin which leads to its stress coping activity, anti-inflammatory, diuretic, immunomodulator, anti-microbial, urogenital activity.

5. *Patala* (*Stereospermum suaveolens*)

- According to Charaka it acts as *Hridya, Vishada*.
- Sushruta included this in *Argvadhadi Gana*.
- The Root Bark of plant *Stereospermum suaveolens* was traditionally used for the treatment of pains and inflammations.^[8]

6. *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cardifolia*)

- Charakacharya included this drug in *Vayasthapana, Stanyashodhana, Dahaprashaman, Trishnanigrahan* and *Chhardinigrahan Gana*.
- Sushrutacharya included in *Patoladi, Kakolyadi, Shyamadi, Guduchyadi, Vallipanchmula, Aragwadhadi Gana*.
- It is *Tridosha Nashak*, therefore helps in all disorders which causes to infertility.
- It is *Rasayana* and *Ayurvedhak*.
- It is *Tridosashamak*, therefore cures all diseases and make women fertile and prevent diseases
- It is said to be antioxidant, anti-bacterial, antifungal, antiviral, cardio protective immune modulator.
- Antioxidant capacity of *Tinospora cordifolia*.^[9]

7. *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula*)

- It works as *Rasayana*.
- Acharya Charaka has kept it into *Prajasthapana, Kushthghna, Arshoghna, Kasaghna, Jwarhara Gana, Shonitsthanadi, Triptighnadi Varga*.

-Anti-microbial activity of Terminalia chebula fruit extract against microorganism. Bacillus subtilis, Staphylococcus aureus, Staphylococcus epidermidis, Escherichia coli, Staphylococcus flexneria and Pseudomonas aeruginosa.^[10]

8. Kutaki (Picrorhiza kurroa)

-Charakacharya enlisted this into *Lekhaniya*, *Bhedniya* and *Stanyashodhana Mahakashaya*.

-Acharya Sushruta has described Kutki in *Pippalyadi*, *Mustadi* and *Patoladi Gana*.

-Acharya Vagbhata included it in *Patoladi Gana*.

-Picrorhiza kurroa (Kutki) is a potent immunostimulant, anti-inflammatory action^[11] antioxidant,^[12] modulates liver enzyme level, anti-allergic action and mild laxative.

9. Bala (Sida cordifolia)

-Charakacharya included this drug in *Bruhaniya*, *Balya*, *Prajasthapana*, *Jivaniyadi*, *Balyadi* and *Shonitsthapanadi Varga*.

-Acharya Sushrut has described *Bala* in *Vidarigandhadi Gana*.

-Sida cordifolia is Rasayana drug generally possesses strong neuroprotective^[13] and Antioxidant^[14] properties.

-It is a Balya tonic and promote reproduction.

-Analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects.^[15]

-It is a good Rasayana herb, as it supplies essential nutrients and strengthen immune system.

10. Priyangu (Callicarpa macrophylla)

-Charakacharya included this drug in *Mutravirajniya*, *Purishsangrahaniya Varga*.

-Acharya Sushruta described Priyangu in *Yelaadi*, *Anjanadi*, *Priyangvaadi Gana*.

-Aqueous as well as ethanolic extracts of leaves of *C. macrophylla* shows anti-inflammatory activity.

-It acts as anti-inflammatory, astringent and rejuvenating properties.^[16]

DISCUSSION

Those drugs who help in conceiving, who act as fertility modulator known As prajasthapana. Keeping all this view now 10 drugs of prajasthapana which are going to be discussed. Brahmi and Aindri which has *medhya prabhav* helps in reducing stress anxiety depression. Present day women are having less strength or power or immunity. Low immunity due to stress, improper diet, abnormal routines and intake of food which is contaminated with chemicals and fertilizers.

CONCLUSION

The objective of the present study entitled a literature review of prajasthapana mahakashaya is to review all 10 drugs of prajasthapana mahakashaya to provide safe and better understanding of drugs included in our study.

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